

Integrating new media to non-commercial media businesses from a project management perspective in Hispanic markets

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Abstract

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Non-commercial radio broadcasting organizations are experiencing a meaningful loss of audience, mainly based on migration to emerging media outlets. Traditional media have shown ineffectiveness in developing strategies integrated into emerging media channels, potentially impacting business opportunities and consumers. Contrary to the commercial media sector, new media integration by the non-commercial industry tends to need improvement. Inquiring into the practices, knowledge, and application of tools and techniques aligned to the Project Management discipline at the non-commercial radio management level helped to understand the potential occurrence. The qualitative research supports comprehension and improves knowledge of how radio broadcasting managers handle migration and manage survivability. Examining the decision-making and operational problems of non-commercial radio broadcasting firm managers' points of view resulted in an enhanced understanding of the ineffectiveness of new media development. The interviewees' answers displayed relevant data that intends to help broadcasting businesses in the new media elaboration, such as podcasts, as part of their product offerings and expansion opportunities. A lack of formal education and training and a sense of urgency are needed. Project management methods and knowledge are recommended based on the significant limitations in the management process, such as planning and executing a new media development task.

Keywords: broadcasting businesses, digital media development, podcasts, project management, radio survivability

Introduction

The research explores the impact of project management tools and techniques on podcast development and integration as a strategy for the non-commercial FM radio broadcasting sector in Puerto Rico. Based on the crucial role of content creation in expanding reach with digital media, such as streaming services and podcast platforms (Sehl, 2020), Understanding the new media practices and tendencies in emerging media outlets should help find the most suitable actions to develop podcasts efficiently. Comprehending how non-commercial broadcasters

operate and manage daily decisions to integrate digital development is vital, and investigating the actual practices of new technology integration to radio organizations should help improve podcast development to optimize the process and potentially increase the survivability of radio as a business.

This qualitative single case study research aimed to describe the integration of emerging media channels into traditional media firms at non-commercial radio stations in Puerto Rico. The continuous increase of new media channel consumption affects the regular operations of a conventional media organization, and businesses should receive research to mitigate the effect and find how to perfect the appropriate adoption processes. According to Kraus, Palment, Kailer, Kallinger, and Spitzer (2019), digital integration into conventional business creates many opportunities and success factors; however, it tends to increase diverse challenges, including low diffusion rates, continuously changing technological atmosphere and non-stop actualization and investment. Inquiring about the participants' experiences integrating new media into their organizations from a projective perspective helped increase effectiveness and efficiency in the incorporation process and may positively affect media survivability. Furthermore, the interpretations of the collected data in the interviews with broadcasters and radio managers of the non-commercial radio broadcasting businesses bring new knowledge that could help integrate new media channel projects for audience improvement, new generations interaction, communication progress, and brand marketing. According to Hysa and Spalek (2018), projects that include innovations in their business strategy are crucial in organizations. However, every new project requires considerable knowledge, communication, and collaboration between businesses and professionals. Therefore, project management skills applied to the integration process of radio firms developing podcasts could be significant for the growth of the audience.

Exploring radio broadcasting's operation management from a project management perspective should help understand and measure the impact of the techniques and methods involved.

Literature Review

The audio media revolution leaves no question that online radio and its variants represent an ongoing innovation and potential prediction of how audio media could behave and consume (Spinelly & Dan, 2019). From a production perspective, several similarities may exist between traditional and online radio formats. Still, several differences exist in the emerging media's acceptance, reception, and consumption. According to Aswad (2017), radio broadcasting is experiencing a massive dislocation from the digital era, and the radio's survival relies on innovation to reduce the impact and maintain its particular place in advertising and stakeholders. Recognizing that the consumer knows best each product or service consumed (Kotler, Keller, & Chernev, 2022) is critical. Developing a program that helps understand how and why the consumer acts is necessary to improve results or maintain the actual status of traditional media-consuming behavior.

According to Chan-Olmsted, Wang, and Hwang (2022), the uncertain future of traditional radio magnifies by its growing irrelevance or insignificance to younger audiences, and its influences are constantly minimized and yield to digital unless it upgrades. Diversification in consumption is among the many factors affecting traditional media as a channel, and the transition from on-air only to adding multiple platforms as part of the firm offerings tends to be a must-do upgrade. The consumer demand, the revenue margins, the competitiveness, and the attraction of an audience that is more fragmented than ever; however, traditional media remains important even with online media gaining relevancy meaningfully (Telkman, 2020).

Technology has dramatically changed how humans act and react to situations with the common factor of internet connection immediately, anywhere, and anytime (Woolley & Sharif, 2022). According to Barrios-Rubio (2021), radio interprets and shares knowledge with society, playing a crucial role as the trans-media agent. Radio can integrate traditional and digital elements by understanding the analogic of audio production, video production, photography, text editing, and print media in a computing and social media strategy atmosphere (Barrios-Rubio, 2021). Incorporating traditional media into the emerging media landscape is essential to survive as a business.

The creative production within almost every FM and AM radio station could become an asset in web-based media such as streaming, podcasting, and even with the live sessions that social media provide, like Facebook Live, Youtube Live, Instagram Live, and Twitter Live tool, previously known as Periscope, if it is managed with the appropriate tools and skills. Radio organizations that organize audio files effectively can enjoy a personalized experience in developing a potential value-added action (Vryzas, Tsipas, & Dimoulas, 2020). Continuous inspection of the diverse processes in any business category to increase efficiency and reduce waste is critical to optimizing success and competitiveness in an increasingly hostile business atmosphere.

Broadcasting to New Media

Mensing (2017) established that broadcasting, customarily used to refer to radio and TV transmission, is gradually replaced by multi-platforms based on the new media landscape. The term broadcasting is traditionally used as part of the traditional media delivery of a set of messages using air as a vehicle from and to an antenna. The transmission of antenna and audio waves is vital to transporting the audio, and it tends to be limited by space and geography. Based on the difference in the delivery and distribution of messages by the media producers of online media, including streaming and podcasting, the term broadcasting may take a lot of work to adapt. Another differentiation between radio broadcasting and podcasting relies on the wording and vocabulary, such as episodes and seasons, rather than time segments or word counting (Spinelly & Dan, 2019). A suspicious discussion about the newness of podcasting compared to the holistic spectrum of radio exists (Morris & Paterson, 2015). However, online radio and its variants are similar to radio from the perspective of 'people-catchers,' advertisement orientation, and audio editing software (Spinelly & Dan, 2019).

Spinelly and Dan (2019) suggested that the production of traditional broadcast media involves an acute awareness of who the target audience is and how specifically they are likely to engage with the content. Radio broadcasts appeal to predetermined audience demographics, trying to satisfy the listener's needs through trial and error. Online radio does not necessarily develop a target audience or run a segmentation based on demographics, psychographics, or geographics at a starting point. Online radio and its variants typically have a topic or category and start talking, hoping to create interest from someone. Spinelly and Dan used the term 'revolutionary' to refer to the new audio-sharing format that integrates web-based platforms that behave differently from other media.

Podcasting

Podcasting is a technology that can distribute, receive, and listen to on-demand audio, usually produced by radio, publishing houses, journalists, educational institutions, and independent producers or radio amateurs (Sullivan, 2019; Bonini, 2015). According to Lissitsa and Laor (2021), podcasts are a popular on-demand audio format in the United States and tend to contain information by topics and increasingly add tools and functions available on the Internet, such as video, pages, and interactions. Podcasting could represent the evolution of audio-only media based on the equipment required and the performance of their producers and talent. A podcast integrates the concept of ‘the iPod,’ a portable media player launched by the firm Apple in 2001 (Apple, 2001), and the concept of ‘broadcast,’ including the option to listen live or at any time. According to Markman (2012), podcasting is a recognized and emerging media that is a powerful tool for creating, communicating, and disseminating audio files. The content of a podcast tends to be diverse and developed by individuals, generally amateurs, and organizations.

Business Practices

Radio broadcasting businesses, including TV, newspapers, and magazines, are part of the traditional media category. According to Torregosa (2000), radio broadcasting started in 1920 after several contributions by inventors such as Heinrich Hertz, James Clerk Maxwell, Guglielmo Marconi, and Nikola Tesla. In November of 1920, the first commercial broadcast began as a medium in America with the 34th presidential election transmission (Torregosa, 2000). In 1922, more than 30 message originators or radio stations originated from East to West in the United States, and the population received half a million radio receivers. According to Klooster (2009), the creation of radio began in the late 1800s. The radio became respected and well-known and gained credibility a few years after its launch. Based on the success of radio broadcasting, the Federal Radio Commission, or FRC, was created in 1927 by the United States government to regulate radio transmissions. In 1934, President Franklin D. Roosevelt Federal signed a federal law called The Communications Act that integrated the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) (Alston, 2021). However, the FCC is still the federal department in charge of admitting, regulating, and giving licenses to media businesses such as radio and TV.

Radio broadcasting started with amplitude-modulated (AM), followed by improvement in technology, equipment, signal, and audio fidelity with frequency-modulated (FM) (Liu et al., 2017). The FCC divided frequencies into commercial and non-commercial licenses depending on the purpose of the organization and the location on the dial. FM radio stations with a commercial license can offer advertising services more flexibly and with limited restrictions by the FCC. Therefore, radio stations that receive non-commercial support can deliver messages similar to ads but without a promotional orientation and limit to mentioning the donors who contribute to the sustainment of the programming as a public service. FCC tends to condemn the commercial practices in a non-commercial licensed radio broadcasting organization with monetary charges, increasing the risk of business operation cancellation.

Radio broadcasting as a business industry had no direct competition until the last decade of the 20th century. The arrival of Satellite Radio with commercial-free programming represented the first real challenge to radio. However, after creative actions and strategic management, radio survived and consistently placed Satellite Radio in permanent second place (Watson, 2019). New characters entered the audio media landscape based on internet connectivity in the new millennium.

The Theory of Uses and Gratifications

Blumler (1979) established that users play a crucial and active role in media consumption. The theory presented gratifications as how individuals actively search for the media that best fits their objectives, stated or not. Some of the searched gratifications include entertainment, culture, and communication styles. Hossain (2018) noted that implementing the uses and gratifications theory could explain why people choose a specific medium and its potential correlation with an aspiration to improve the understanding of society and individuals.

Digital media interaction is a game-changer and critical in new media development and management. According to Rolland, Mathianssen, and Rai (2018), organizations increasingly use digital platforms to implement innovation and try to understand how platforms shape the business’s strategic plans and actions. Craig, Brooks, and Bichard (2021) stated that entertainment strongly forecasts new media attention and attraction, specifically by listening as entertainment and escaping mechanism by university students. The integration of the theory of uses and gratification could be appropriate for podcast development based on the results of the study showing favorable attitudes of the participants (Craig et al., 2021). Based on the digital media motivation in uses and gratifications theory, podcasts have become one of the digital media closest to youth (Stephanie, Rachmawaty, & Dyanasari, 2021). Determining the main

factor and motivation of the target market of the new media development is essential to increase effectiveness and maximize the few resources available, even more in a non-commercial broadcasting organization. According to Stephanie et al. (2021), young people tend to listen to podcasts and digital audio media similar to the practice of listening to the radio, including but not limited to driving or walking from point A to point B, studying, or making assignments, and academic tasks and spending leisure time.

According to Kamboj (2020), the theory of uses and gratifications presents a unique significance to digital media management, showing a vivid and rich understanding of why customers use new media platforms. As part of broad digital ecosystems, emerging media platforms, including podcasts in context, provide many gratifications in diverse areas, such as brand likeability. Brand commitment and word-of-mouth are the principal integration of the digital ecosystems' theory of uses and gratifications, bundling with an opportunity to invest over time. (Kamboj, 2020).

Perks and Turner (2018) stated that podcasts provide an endless supply of engaging material with a particular capacity for traveling with the listener. Perks and Turner also suggested that the mobility podcast consumption on the move offers the listeners the opportunity to increase productivity in diverse areas, such as physical and mental. The enjoyment could come from the relationship between podcast hosts and other listeners' communities. According to Kujur and Singh (2020), a particular media channel gratifies the audience and the population's need for information, entertainment, and incentives. People have different motives for consuming audiovisual content related to a specific brand. Still, companies use the theory of uses and gratifications as a foundation to actively search for increasing engagement. Traditional media managers, broadcasters, and the radio broadcasting industry should examine the business opportunities available, including new environments of interaction that could result in new business development, engagement-increasing opportunities, and potential innovative income sources.

The Media Dependency Theory

Ball-Rokeach and DeFlour (1976) stated a natural and functional relationship exists between audiences and media. The media dependency theory suggests that media tend to fulfill the audience actively, and audiences do the same to media as a loop. The media dependency theory is built on cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects. The cognitive integrates how media could manipulate intentionally or unintentionally changes in attitudes, beliefs, and values. The effectiveness relates to the feelings perceived after exposing information such as news. The behavioral effect is present when a media firm looks to motivate its audience to act or react to something. According to Dwivedi et al. (2021), the more a user becomes dependent on a medium or media to satisfy the needs of information, entertainment, and socialization, the more the medium should influence the user facilitating the process of establishing or implementing the media agenda.

The media dependency theory could be more of a protagonist in the social media era. According to Kim and Jung (2017), interpersonal narrative, including social media, corresponds to post-exposure communication. People exposed to a message because of high-level reliance on the media tend likely to initiate or participate in post-exposure conversations about topics they have experienced. Post-exposure also implies starting and communicating with close people, understanding family and friends, and sharing issues in various scenarios, such as status messages published on social media platforms.

According to Kim and Jung (2017), the concept of post-exposure communication complements the concept of interpersonal narration in many areas. Media dependency theory proposes a positive relationship between narrative and action. People who can talk about a specific topic are more likely to act and use the most recent information to which they have been exposed, probably unconsciously. The increasing internet connectivity and device usage could add a new layer of media dependency to the established theory. More consumers initiate or amplify social media usage for daily activities such as reading the news, researching products, and entertaining themselves (Dwivedi et al., 2021; GlobalWebIndex Social Flagship Report, 2019). Companies must strategically design, coordinate, and implement a social media management plan to appeal to their target audiences more effectively.

Media owners should study the media dependency theory, focusing on ethically using audience behavior to increase consumption and engagement levels and potentially reduce viewers and listeners. However, based on the statement by Leblanc (2017), commercial media organizations' purpose is only to make a profit, so the theory in discussion could be used negatively. Developing new media, such as podcasts by radio broadcasting organizations with adequate knowledge and ethical levels, could help achieve goals.

The Innovation Diffusion Theory

Rogers (1962) stated how an idea could be spread to the population with an appropriate communication plan. According to Dearing and Cox (2018), diffusion is a social process that occurs among people in response to learning

about an innovative aspect or subject, such as new approaches or findings as research results and involves a communication aspect that transcends over time among the members of a social system. Kreps (2017) suggested that this theory should help communities and societies mitigate uncertainty and lack of knowledge about specific and challenging issues. Innovative diffusion brings a direction for achieving social goals and increases the chances of progress in updated and more civilized societies. Diffusion is a critical communication process reflecting and disseminating information about new ideas, products, technologies, services, or regulations, promoting social progress to address specific issues. Diffusion helps reduce uncertainty about handling complex problems and includes direction for achieving individual and collective goals.

According to Sirk (2020), the characteristics of innovation influence its chances of adoption by the population. The most relevant elements influencing the adoption of novelties are complexity, adaptability, compatibility, and reliability, and holistically could contribute to a relative advantage. Another relevant aspect that Sirk (2020) suggested is trialability, referring to the ability of individuals or groups to try an unknown alternative. The openness to trying out new things is essential in the innovation process. Broadcasters should prepare to take a risk in the developing process of emerging media that could become a part of the solution to the losing audience issue.

Sirk (2020) stated that communication is vital in diffusion because new technologies and concepts must spread by word of mouth and added to other communication channels such as mass media and social network platforms. Broadcasting allowed traditional media firms to share new information with individuals. Meanwhile, social media channels tend to operate from individual to individual in a more personal way. Broadcasting and social networks result in relevancy based on the time of adoption of the innovations that could appear slow. Sirk (2020) suggested five stages of the adoption process that could be useful for a traditional and digital media manager to execute new technologies and innovative changes. The five stages of Sirk (2020) are awareness, persuasion, decision, implementation, and continuation.

The Administrative Management Theory

Henri Fayol, the founder, and father of modern management, firmly believes in and study how leadership can be segmented into specific patterns as common factors (Kitana, 2016). According to the Chartered Manager Institute (2012) and Henri Fayol (1949), six activity groups segment to classify the management types better. Those six groups are technical include (a) professional areas such as engineering, production, manufacturing, and adaptation; (b) commercial referring to areas such as buying, selling, and exchanges; financial related to the search for the best use of capital; and (c) security that relates to the protection of assets and personnel. In addition, the six groups include (a) accounting, which includes stocktaking, balance sheets, costs, and statistics; and (b) managerial, allowing the planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and controlling processes. Fayol (1949) emphasizes the managerial to develop a business strategic plan. Fayol summarized the essential management application to planning, organizing, commanding, coordination, and control as part of the administrative activity investigation.

Some authors relate management to art or science. However, it is a practical subject based on the intentional learning process guided by experience and acquired knowledge (Mintzberg, 2019). Managers are responsible for designing and maintaining an appropriate environment to fulfill the firm's purpose and aspirations. Managing is an essential activity at all levels. According to Mintzberg (2019), management is not considered a science, art, or craft; it's an application process of adequate experiences rooted in context founded on effectiveness. Many theories about management include classical, neo-classical, systematic, behavioral, scientific, and modern (Kitana, 2016). Still, the conceptualization built by Fayol is one of the complete and most used by businesses. Based on the potential need for management skills to develop new media, such as podcasts by traditional media organizations, it is vital to examine the most efficient practices in the field to increase the chances of success.

Fayol (1949) also established 14 principles of administration management. Using the Fayol research-based principles may help broadcasting media managers in their daily operational tasks, including the potential new requirements in the new media development process. According to the Chartered Manager Institute (2012), the 14 principles include division of labor, authority, discipline, command unit, address unit, subordination, remuneration, centralization, hierarchy, order, equity, staff stability, initiative, and staff union.

Division of Labor. The division of labor includes segmenting the tasks necessary for producing a good into smaller tasks. The evaluation of the division of work must base on strength, work ability, specialty, and the nature of the job to improve the whole endeavor. The efficiency orientations provided by project management tools, such as work breakdown structure, should help with the crucial fragmentation of work in tasks needed to develop digital media content.

Authority. The authority principle is essential to finish the job and avoid a mess. Besides, authority tends to help carry out the proper quality levels and predetermined deadlines. Establishing a timetable with specific instructions and appropriate direction is necessary to increase quality and reduce time or budget. A team leader expected the broadcasting manager to apply the guidance needed to complete the podcast development process effectively.

Discipline. In addition to authority, the principle of discipline establishes that all processes must be performed in a solid field. It is useless to know what to do if it is limited to that and not fulfill it. Discipline is a characteristic that should be present in every team member but must be shown by the team leader. Working consistently from an optimization perspective could become a habit that team members emulate.

Command Unit. A single superior or designated management-level team leader must dictate the orders, and instructions. This principle's absence could negatively affect other principles, such as authority and discipline. Teams that received instructions from multiple leaders could increase confusion and potentially reduce efficiency.

Address Unit. All the activities should pursue a similar objective, and the same superior should direct the activities. Establishing goals is essential for any project., Communicating the purpose clearly and from a unique source of authority and information should result in significant achievements and optimal podcast development.

Subordination. The organization's goals are more important than personal or individual goals. The appropriate coordination and communication of the firms or project goals could be crucial to avoiding protagonists. Increasing the importance of the team members' contribution to podcast development projects is essential.

Remuneration. This principle states that income is necessary, but no ideal payment system exists. The firm must balance motivating the personnel to work with adequate salaries without affecting productivity. Motivation plays a relevant role in the project's progress, and the proper compensation should help fulfill personnel needs, personally and professionally, improving the podcast development process.

Centralization. Improving the organizational results predicates on the concentration of company management. However, sometimes, it is more convenient and practical to decentralize and resort to delegation. Managers must identify the most suitable approach to podcast development as a potential business opportunity. Strategic planning should include centralization or decentralization as part of the decision-making process.

Hierarchy. Authority tends to travel from top to bottom in a firm with a vertical organization chart with different levels of command. Team members should respect the levels of authority and not jump. The team member must use the communication channels appropriately and in order. Recognizing the authority levels delimited by the job description could benefit the podcasting project by allowing the team members to focus on the assigned tasks.

Order. The necessary resources for the organization's activity must occur at the right time and place. The essence of project management is the just-in-time foundation to increase effectiveness and efficiency. Planning and coordinating the resources and tools needed to develop innovation, such as new media products, is critical and should reduce the chances of failure.

Equity. To maintain coherence and obtain results, the treatment of personnel must be as fair and respectful as possible. Independent of the level of position in a firm, all people deserve the same respect and should be treated as colleagues. Recognizing the organizational levels tends to help, but elevating the respect levels to the highest is more critical.

Staff Stability. In line with the division of labor, it is considered convenient for the staff to remain in their positions for the long term. Changing personnel means increasing the cost of training new employees and waiting for them to adapt. Besides, job stability could improve productivity. Project management i reflects increasing quality aspects and reducing costs and time. In developing online audio media such as podcasts, taking care of the team members that started the project is the recommended recommendation based on all the costs that hiring and training time involved.

Initiative. Anyone at any level of the organization can suggest ideas that must be well- received and valued. Four eyes see more than two, and two heads think better than one. Communication is essential, and an optimal team tends to communicate ideas more effectively, knowing that their thoughts receive consideration. The principal suggestion is that a potential solution or optimal way of developing a podcast could come from a member of the lower level of the project. Having the maturity and critical thinking to accept a rejection of an idea is also essential to completing the project efficiently.

Staff Union. A team atmosphere must exist. If everyone rows in the same direction, the boat should reach the port safely and quickly. As stated, podcast development is a collaborative task that needs the best team formation possible. Understanding that a successful podcast project happens with the value contribution of team members' work is vital to maximizing the development of new media products.

According to Mintzberg (2019), a manager handles the whole organization and helps holistically bring the best outcome possible from the employees and the firm by knowing better, deciding better, and executing better. Fayol's 14 principles are typically used as a foundation to build management levels in many companies. Realizing that having the best management practices must help in podcast development by a radio broadcasting company is critical, even with the potential tasks added to the person in charge. Effective managers are not those with the most significant degrees of freedom but those who take advantage of whatever degree of freedom they find (Mintzberg, 2019). Managers tend to admit that no one is better at business procedures, including time management than themselves (Browne et al., 2018), which could be a significant bias. Radio broadcasting managers' daily practices may be repeated, and their thoughts of knowing the tasks to satiety could potentially limit the possible new ways of doing things. Returning to the management foundation of Fayol's principles and the administrative management theory is essential in a changed media atmosphere.

The in-depth academic literature review brings a better overview of the existing studies and theories related to the research. The literature review provides an appropriate foundation for a more effective examination of the factors that could affect or relate to the topic of podcasting development by radio broadcasting organizations. The changes in radio broadcasting audience consumption, mainly because of increased online media usage, have significantly affected the traditional media business. Starting or establishing strategic planning from the management of conventional broadcasting-level firms is critical and reliable and increases the chances of survivability. Podcasting developed by traditional media from a project management perspective could be helpful based on the tight budget that non-commercial radio stations tend to manage. Adding responsibilities to the radio managers may affect their daily performance and work schedule, so the voluntary work from employees must not be rejected to reduce costs related to hiring, time, and training, among others.

Understanding the different consumption scenarios from a generational perspective tends to reflect an adequate audience that supports online media content. Young audiences are more connected to the Internet and tend to reject traditional media as a way of expression, interest in innovation, or simply a commodity. The versatility of online radio, including streaming, satellite radio, and podcasting, could represent an added business opportunity for radio broadcasting organizations. Freedom and on-demand access are some of the characteristics that online audio media present and should be a potential evolution of conventional radio if managed correctly. The assumptions and specific description of podcasting revealed that, technically, it is similar to radio production and programming techniques, representing a less challenging development for a new business category specializing in audio production. Another advantage is the aspect of the producers and hosts creating podcasts that are typically radio-background professionals and innovators with a particular technology ambition.

Related Studies

Several studies exist on radio broadcasting and podcasting processes, but only a few are from a project management perspective. However, reviewing the data obtained by participants could play an essential role in this study. It is critical to align the theories associated with the study with project management as a tool.

Perks and Turner (2018) studied how the theory of uses and Gratifications is related to podcasting compared to traditional media. The Theory of Uses and gratifications placed users as crucial players with an active role in media consumption (Blumler, 1979). The theory established that individuals seek the most suitable media for their expectations and goals related to

entertainment, culture, and communication. Several gratifications in podcasting compared to radio broadcasting, such as multitasking during boring activities and immersion in a story similar to transportation to another world (Perks & Turner, 2018). According to Perks and Turner (2018), podcasting could serve as a cognitive brain feeder and advantage AM and FM radio because of its capacity for better mobility, increased social aspect, and better individualized content choice-making. Podcasting is assumed as an audience-motivated system with a unique freedom of selection by individuals actively searching to meet their self-identified needs.

Allen (2020) explored how the radio broadcasting industry faces new and increasing challenges from a commercial point of view. The Theory of broadcasting media concentration and commercial advertising suggests that broadcasters' profit-maximizing response increases industry concentration (Cunningham & Alexander, 2004). Increased advertising in broadcast media industries such as radio may decrease the total amount of non-advertising broadcasting. Organizations that invest in non-advertising or non-commercial campaigns reduce their advertising effort and budget. Radio is a type of business with structured programming funded by commercials or public subsidies (Bonet & Sellas, 2019). Non-commercial radio broadcasting experienced several challenges based on the FCC's

limitations of commercial actions. Developing podcasts could represent new business opportunities that the FCC does not regulate but potentially work as part of the business.

Regarding profitability, adapting to new consumer behaviors by adopting new media such as podcasts could help radio station businesses urgently need changes (Allen, 2020). According to Allen (2020), developing digital space allows potential buyers to have on-air radio advertisement campaigns and complement social media, websites, and endorsement interactions. Sales, promotion, and programming are an integral part of a radio broadcasting business, and

there is no radio without them, especially sales (Allen, 2020). The appropriate application of project management techniques and tools could increase effectiveness and efficiency in sales, promotion, and programming integration to develop podcasting.

According to Bonet and Sellas (2019), digitalization, which includes the radio business, represents an intellectual challenge for the political economy of the cultural industry. Digitalizing means shifting the focus towards video, audio, and text, and after the process is complete, the content becomes standardized and requires careful management (Bonet & Sellas, 2019). The new management layer needed different techniques and methodologies and added characters, intermediaries, and sources based on the technology universalization where anyone can produce and broadcast (Bonet & Sellas, 2019). Allen (2020) established that programming is the main product of radio stations to audiences and advertisers. Bonet and Sellas (2019) suggested that managing digital aspects offers an area of experimentation, freedom, and rehearsal of content but also has limitations with the non-standard duration of programs and *broadcast structure* that include jingles, music instrumentals or beds, and timing. The innovation diffusion theory (Rogers, 1962) established that the audience or population adopts new behaviors edge by social systems. Based on the innovation diffusion theory, radio broadcasting should pay attention to the audience's behavior guided by society and be receptive to innovations even when they include management changes. According to Johnston and Brennan (1996), a strong connection exists between management's actions and the firm's results. Programming requires strategic planning and management. A professional who is attentive to changes in the media environment and is open to learning new techniques and methodologies is vital in today's media landscape (Bonet & Sellas, 2019).

Materials and Methods

The studied sample includes 10 participants who met the requirements of 18 years or older in a managerial decision-making position for at least three years. The potential 15 candidates who resumed the non-commercial FM radio in Puerto Rico were reduced to ten based on failing to meet the established requirements. The pseudonyms for the participant's name are masked as Broadcaster 1, Broadcaster 2, Broadcaster 3, and so on for protection and chronologically in a linear narrative. The order of the interviews was random and based on the responses and availability of the participants between March 2023 and September 2023. The number assigned to the participant was explicitly the order of the performed interview arranged by date. The number given or code also protects the individuals if delicate information is asked or mentioned, such as a radio firm's business strategy. The interview process occurred in a first round of three weeks, added to a second round of two weeks that added the remaining participants to reach the proposed ten candidates that fulfill the requirements. The interview questions were founded on how radio managers manage their daily decisional process based on the traditional media challenges, their perspective on adopting new media channels as part of the product offerings, and their knowledge of Project Management techniques and tools to handle new tasks. The interviewing process ended when the participant's list was complete and satisfied after several actions to find newly aligned candidates.

Results

This qualitative research single case study included understanding how project management tools and techniques interfere with new media development by non-commercial FM radio broadcasting firms in Puerto Rico markets as a primary purpose. Based on the variable behavior of media consumers and the significant audience migration from traditional to digital media, examining the effectiveness of web-based media integration by non-commercial radio broadcasting managers as participants was essential. Non-commercial radio broadcasting organizations tend to experience a more complex scenario than commercial radio broadcasting organizations because of the regulations imposed by the Federal Communications Commission as a primary factor. The more significant problem addressed was the knowledge of project tools and techniques to foster new media, such as podcasts, that could improve the highly challenging atmosphere for non-commercial radio broadcasters in Puerto Rico. The latest media landscape is more extensive, hostile, and competitive, reducing the chances of success as a business to a traditional media outlet if

the integration of web-based platforms is minimal or absent. The lack of knowledge of effective methodologies for digital media integration resulted in the inability to compete in the new media atmosphere in Hispanic markets. Non-commercial radio broadcasting businesses' management-level work points to collecting firsthand data related to leadership and knowledge of effectiveness in the decision-making process. Besides, the participants' answers and proper analysis elevated comprehension of how media managers realize and apply optimal techniques in their daily duties and their contribution to new media development. Collecting data from the non-commercial radio broadcasting managers through semistructured interviews provided valuable feedback that helped understand the ineffectiveness of podcasting integration. The interpretation of the collected data showed that over 80% of the participants needed more knowledge of the Project Management tools and methodologies, much less applying effective and efficient practices to improve the business processes. The participant tended to bet on the current and antique practices to survive in a new and more competitive business environment. Over 70% concurred that new media development is a critical component of their business survival. However, 90% of the interviewees perceived the new media actualization as an organic process that does not require urgency, appropriate tools, or innovative knowledge or training.

Relevant themes are directly associated with the conflicts that non-commercial radio broadcasting firms experience in remaining competitive and as an option to the actual media consumer. The findings showed that a sense of urgency, applying effective and efficient methodologies, and formal education or training were minimal or absent among non-commercial broadcasters in Puerto Rico. Establishing a plan that includes project management tools and technical preparation should help reduce time and increase quality in adopting new media. Acquiring leadership skills, formal or informal, is vital to a traditional media manager to achieve business objectives such as developing products ready for consumption. Leadership and strategy play a significant role at the management level, as well as managing media business with solid integrity principles and values for long-term performance and higher chances of survivability. This study's results helped better understand how non-commercial radio broadcasting managers operate and why their performance is perceived as ineffective based on the contemporary digital migration levels. This research should contribute to the non-commercial and commercial radio broadcasting managers recognizing the importance of developing new media, mainly web-based platforms, to increase new generation audience listenership and reach, traditional brand awareness, consumer engagement tendencies, and more accurate business analysis to compete and coexist in the latest social consumption behavior and media landscape.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework. Source: Rosado (2023)

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